

Synthesis of some 2,4-Diamino 6-(substituted)-amino-5-arylazopyrimidines and their Effect on the Growth of *S. faecalis*

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A number of 5-arylazopyrimidines have been prepared by coupling 2,4-diamino-6-(substituted)-aminopyrimidines with diazotised arylamines and their effect on the growth of *Streptococcus faecalis* has been reported. Investigations show that the above compounds inhibit the growth of *S. faecalis* and act as folic acid antagonists. The growth inhibition has also been compared with that produced by 5-unsubstituted compounds and some well known antibiotics.

IN course of our previous work, we synthesised various kinds of purine and pyrimidine derivatives¹⁻⁶ with the hope of getting compounds having antagonistic activity on nucleic acid metabolism. Many of the compounds synthesised by us were found to inhibit the growth of *S. faecalis* and other organisms⁷⁻¹⁰.

It was observed that the presence of amino group at 2- and 4-positions of the pyrimidine ring was probably responsible for antimicrobial activity. Further, a number of 5-arylazopyrimidines have been found to possess interesting antifolic, antimicrobial, antimalarial and anticancer properties¹¹⁻¹⁷. Pyrimidines having an amino and/or hydroxyl group at C-2 and C-4 positions and a bulky substituted amino group at C-6 position have been found to inhibit the growth of some microorganisms^{18,19}. 2,4-Diamino-6-*p*-bromoanilino-5-nitropyrimidine has been found to exhibit activity against Walker 256 (WM) tumor system²⁰. In view of the above observations, we became interested in studying the effect of introducing an arylazo group in 5-position and a bulky substituted amino group in 6-position of 2,4-diaminopyrimidine moiety on the biological properties of resultant compounds and our compounds (1-24 reported in the present paper) were synthesised with that view.

These synthetic pyrimidines have been tested against *S. faecalis* and their growth inhibitory activity has been compared with that of 5-unsubstituted pyrimidines (Type A) and also with some well known antibiotics.

The new 5-arylazopyrimidines (1-24) were obtained by the coupling reaction of an appropriate 2,4,6-trisubstituted pyrimidine (A) with diazotised arylamine at 2-5° and pH 5-6 or 8-9 depending on the nature of the 5-unsubstituted compound used. Proper maintenance of pH was found to be essential for the reaction. The 5-arylazopyrimidines are all coloured crystalline solids and almost all the compounds are insoluble in common organic solvents at room temperature. The compounds prepared are listed in Table 1.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in capillary tubes on a copper block. M. ps. of the compounds that melted with decomposition were determined by rapidly heating the block to about 20° below the actual m.p. and then heating the block at the rate of $\sim 4^{\circ} \text{min}^{-1}$. All the melting points reported are corrected. In crystallisation, the term alcohol always refers to 90% (w/w) ethanol. Uv spectra were recorded in absolute ethanol on a Cary 17D spectrophotometer. Before elemental analysis, the compounds were dried over P_2O_5 at 110°/1 mm for 16 h.

All the 2,4-diamino-6-(substituted-amino)pyrimidines, used as starting materials, were prepared according to the known methods^{8,21} except 2,4-diamino-6-morpholino compound which was prepared as follows.

A mixture of 2,4-diamino-6-chloropyrimidine²² (0.0069 mol) and anhydrous morpholine (0.034 mol) was slowly heated for 1 h to 130° (oil-bath temp.) and then kept at this temperature for further 2.5 h. The solid soon went into solution and a viscous substance resulted. The product was extracted with boiling toluene (2 × 20 ml). The toluene extracts were combined and slightly concentrated. On

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TABLE 1—PHYSICAL CONSTANTS AND DATA ON GROWTH-INHIBITION AND ITS REVERSAL BY PGA FOR 5-ARYLAZOPYRIMIDINES (1-24, STRUCTURE B)

Compd. no.	R ₂	Yield %	M.p. °C	Colour	Molecular formula	λ _{max} (log ε)	Inhibitor concn. (μg ml ⁻¹) required for 50% inhibition of <i>S. faecalis</i> growth†	Percent growth* with increasing concn. of PGA**	
								1	20
R ₁ = <i>p</i> -Iodophenylamino									
1	<i>p</i> -Br	87.2	300 d	Yellow needles	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₇ BrI	204(5.05) 256(4.78) 284(4.81) 428(4.56)	<i>a</i>	—	—
2	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	85.2	250 d	Yellow powder	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₇ I	202(4.76) 254(4.41) 290(4.62) 400(4.51)	<i>b</i>	—	—
3	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	72.4	246 d	Yellow powder	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₇ OI	208(4.72) 292(4.49) 397(4.22)	<i>c</i>	—	—
4	<i>m</i> -OCH ₃	83.7	223 d	Yellow powder	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₇ OI	202(4.49) 255(4.17) 290(4.48) 400(4.37) 420(4.39)	<i>b</i>	—	—
5	<i>p</i> -SO ₃ H	84.6	283 d	Yellow powder	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₇ SO ₃ I	254(4.25) 288(4.40) 428(4.28)	4.8	22	79
R ₁ = <i>p</i> -Anisidino									
6	<i>p</i> -Br	87.0	233 d	Deep yellow powder	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ N ₇ OBr	204(3.95) 232(3.67) 274(3.67) 430(3.26)	<i>c</i>	—	—
7	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	88.7	214	Yellow powder	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₇ O	228(3.77) 256(3.99) 280(4.14) 3.96(4.07)	<i>d</i>	—	—
8	<i>o</i> -OCH ₃	81.0	119 d	Golden yellow shining crystals	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₇ O ₂	202(4.52) 250(4.09) 286(4.30) 442(4.28)	<i>e</i>	—	—
9	<i>m</i> -OCH ₃	82.3	166 d	Yellow powder	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ N ₇ O ₂	204(5.15) 276(4.85) 428(4.54)	<i>b</i>	—	—
10	<i>p</i> -SO ₃ H	89.1	265 d	Orange powder	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₇ SO ₃	202(4.76) 252(4.40) 276(4.46) 428(4.25)	0.43	11	68
R ₁ = Cyclohexylamino									
11	<i>p</i> -Br	77.5	210	Yellow shining needles	C ₁₆ H ₂₀ N ₇ Br	202(4.25) 258(4.12) 388(4.24)	0.62	17	75
12	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	79.4	182	Yellow shining needles	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ N ₇	204(4.00) 256(4.19) 392(4.29)	0.30	18	71
13	<i>m</i> -OCH ₃	71.4	174	Yellow crystals	C ₁₇ H ₂₂ N ₇ O	204(4.10) 258(4.38) 388(4.42)	1.34	26	82
14	<i>p</i> -SO ₃ H	79.7	309 d	Yellow powder	C ₁₆ H ₂₁ N ₇ SO ₃	211(4.50) 264(4.28) 394(4.39)	<i>f</i>	—	—
R ₁ = Piperidino									
15	<i>p</i> -Br	90.3	215	Orange shining plates	C ₁₆ H ₁₈ N ₇ Br	202(4.69) 213(4.63) 229(4.61) 271(4.58) 396(4.73)	<i>b</i>	—	—

(Table 1 contd.)

16	<i>o</i> -OH ₂	88.1	222 d	Orange shining needles	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₇	240(4.28) 282(4.34) 395(4.36)	1.91	6	62
17	<i>o</i> -OOH ₂	88.5	174	Brown shining needles	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₇ O	245(3.97) 285(4.21) 325(3.74) 402(4.32)	100	15	73
18	<i>m</i> -OOH ₂	84.9	164	Orange shining plates	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₇ O	205(4.91) 270(4.71) 394(4.81)	58.0	28	77
19	<i>p</i> -SO ₃ H	84.9	247 d	Yellow powder	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₇ SO ₃	202(4.98) 224(4.87) 270(4.62) 394(4.53)	<i>g</i>	—	—
R ₁ = Morpholino									
20	<i>p</i> -Br	75.3	239 d	Orange shining crystals	C ₁₄ H ₁₆ N ₇ BrO	204(4.29) 234(4.15) 258(4.04) 272(4.03) 392(4.26)	40.0	12	71
21	<i>o</i> -OH ₂	54.8	187	Yellow shining needles	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₇ O	204(4.45) 272(3.19) 392(4.40)	72.0	19	74
22	<i>o</i> -OOH ₂	47.4	201 d	Orange shining needles	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₇ O ₂	204(4.47) 275(4.34) 400(4.48)	14.75	22	73
23	<i>m</i> -OOH ₂	94.0	171	Orange shining crystals	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₇ O ₂	210(4.19) 275(3.99) 394(4.05)	30.5	26	80
24	<i>p</i> -SO ₃ H	89.5	243 d	Yellow powder	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ N ₇ SO ₃	204(5.04) 232(4.82) 255(4.64) 285(4.45) 390(4.10)	<i>c</i>	—	—
2,4-Diamino-6- <i>p</i> -iodo-anilinopyrimidine							15.9		
2,4-Diamino-6- <i>p</i> -anisidinopyrimidine							85.0		
2,4-Diamino-6-cyclohexylaminopyrimidine							82.0		
2,4-Diamino-6-piperidinopyrimidine							154.0		
2,4-Diamino-6-morpholinopyrimidine							365.0		
Chloramphenicol							2.15		
Tetracycline							14.25		
Streptomycin							<i>h</i>		
Neomycin							<i>h</i>		

Satisfactory analytical data for C, H and N has been obtained for all the compounds. For purification, 1-4 and 6-9 were crystallised from glacial AcHO, 9-12 20-22 from alcohol, 13, 23 from absolute alcohol, 15 from pyridine water, 16-18 from alcohol-water, 5, 10, 14, 19 and 24 purified by dissolving in NaHCO₃ solution and precipitating by acidifying with dilute HCl.

† PGA medium (PAG concn. 1.0 m μ g ml⁻¹ allowing half maximal growth). * Maximum growth with optimum amount of PGA (3 m μ g ml⁻¹) and without inhibitor taken as 100%. ** The growth is restored gradually with increasing concentration of PGA. However, only the data with 20 m μ g ml⁻¹ of PGA has been incorporated in the table because maximum reversal of growth occurs at this concentration of PGA. The reversal studies were made at the inhibitor concentration indicated in column 7.

[i.e., the half-inhibitory concentration at a PGA level of 1 m μ g ml⁻¹]

a-g No inhibition upto 30, 100, 200, 300, 50, 120, 80 μ g ml⁻¹, respectively. Higher concentration than indicated could not be used owing to low solubility of the compounds. *h* Little or no activity

cooling, the title compound crystallised out. It was further purified by crystallisation from toluene as white needles, (0.84 g, 62.40%), m.p. 184° (Found : C, 49.34 ; H, 6.28 ; N, 36.01. $C_8H_{18}N_2O$ requires : C, 49.22 ; H, 6.66 ; N, 35.89%).

5-Arylazopyrimidines (1-24) : *General method of preparation :* A solution of 2,4,6-trisubstituted-pyrimidine (0.00215 mol) was prepared by adding glacial acetic acid drop by drop with stirring to a suspension of the compound in water (100 ml) (2,4-diamino-6-cyclohexylaminopyrimidine and 2,4-diamino-6-morpholinopyrimidine dissolved in water without addition of glacial acetic acid). An ice-cold solution of an equimolar amount of the diazotised arylamine [prepared by adding a cold solution of 0.00215 mol sodium nitrite in water (5 ml) with stirring to an ice-cold solution of 0.00215 mol of the amine in 10 ml 1N HCl ; the diazotised solution must contain excess of HCl] was slowly added to the pyrimidine solution with stirring. The stirring was continued and after 5 min 2N NaOH solution was added dropwise to bring pH of the reaction solution to 8-9, when a heavy precipitate appeared. Stirring was further continued for 4 h. (In the case of compounds 5, 10, 14, 19 and 24, the solution became coloured at pH 8-9 instead of giving precipitate. In these cases after stirring for 4 h, dilute HCl was added dropwise to bring the pH to 5-6 when a heavy precipitate appeared). The product was filtered, washed several times with water, dried at 80° (compounds 5, 10, 14, 19 and 24 were, however, dried directly after filtration without washing) and purified (cf. foot-note to Table 1).

Inhibition of growth of microorganism :

Assay method : All compounds were tested for antimicrobial activity against *Streptococcus faecalis* ATCC 8043. To a series of culture tubes containing different amounts of each inhibitor, basal medium^{23,24} (5 ml) and folic acid were added and the volume was made upto 10 ml with water. After sterilisation, inoculation and incubation (18 h), growth was measured as turbidity with a Klett-Summerson photoelectric colorimeter. From the growth curve (Klett reading vs inhibitor concentration), half inhibitory concentration was determined by noting the inhibitor concentration at 50% inhibition of standard growth (Table 1). The solubilities of the compounds 1-4, 6-9, 14, 15, 19 and 24 were low and not sufficient for determination of 50% inhibition of growth.

Reversal studies : To a series of tubes containing a specific amount of the inhibitor and basal medium (5 ml), increasing amounts of PGA were added and the volume was made upto 10 ml. The amount of growth at different concentrations of PGA were noted.

Results

The results (Table 1) show that the synthesised 5-aryazo compounds inhibit the growth of *S.*

faecalis. A comparison of the inhibitory activity of the compounds with the 5-unsubstituted compounds shows that a 5-aryazo group imparts additional growth inhibitory power. The antimicrobial activity depends on the nature of the substituent in the 6-position and also on the nature of the substituent on the phenyl ring in the 5-position.

The results of reversal studies in Table 1 (column 8) also show that the growth inhibitory action of the compounds can be reversed by increasing concentrations of PGA. The 5-arylazopyrimidines can, therefore, be regarded as specific antagonists of folic acid. All these compounds have a common structural feature (they all contain a 2,4-diaminopyrimidine moiety), which is very similar to the 2-amino-4-hydroxypyrimidine moiety present in PGA. It is, therefore, probable that the 2,4-diaminopyrimidine moiety present in the above types of compounds is responsible for binding of the compounds at the active site of an enzyme for which folic acid acts as a substrate.

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